

STUDY OF IMPACTED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES BY MEANS OF THE RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY.

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SUMMARY: An experimental method, called the response surface method, is used to study the response of laminated and sandwich composite structures under impact loading (low velocity-high mass). For the laminated composites, the importance of the mass, velocity of the striker is studied for different responses such as the contact force between striker and composite structure, the displacement of the projectile, the time of contact and the damage within the composite structure. For the sandwich composites, the influence of the span of the structure is additionally considered. The evolution of the contact force is more particularly analysed. The results illustrate how this technique improves the understanding of the behaviour of impacted composite structures for designing. They underline that the kinetic energy of the striker should not always be considered as a representative parameter of the studied response of composite structures under impact loading.

KEYWORDS: impact, laminated structures, sandwich structures, response surface method, cracking, delamination, drop-weight set-up, Doehlert matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Impact (low velocity-high mass) is a multi-parameter problem. Therefore, analytical models to represent the mechanical or physical responses of composite structures are not easy to propose. The evolution of responses as a function of variables is modelled by simple mathematical expressions (empirical polynomials) but these are not based on physical mechanisms. In this study, impact loading can be defined in terms of the geometry, mass and speed of the striker, the size of the composite plate, and the boundary conditions [1-6]. The influence of plate dimensions is rarely studied. In addition, the critical parameter used to characterise an impact is the kinetic energy of the striker rather than the mass-velocity combination [7]. The importance of the mass, velocity of the striker and the span of the composite structure is studied for different responses such as the contact force between striker and composite structure, the displacement of the projectile, and the damage within the

composite structure. These enable different variables to be assessed and the most influential ones to be identified with a minimum of experiments.

METHODOLOGY

An analysis of the influence of the mass and speed of the striker was first performed by means of laminated composite structures. Then sandwich structures were used to establish empirical polynomial models linking the mass, speed of the striker and the span of the composite plate to the mechanical responses in a given experimental domain.

In order to demonstrate mechanical, physical or chemical phenomena tests are frequently performed, in small or large numbers. The experimental design method enables test campaigns to be set up to minimise variance in results while reducing the number of tests.

By analysing the results from such tests empirical polynomial models can be established relating the variables of the mechanical system to the structural responses. The basis of this approach lies in the fact that the model variance (Eqn 1) can be expressed as the product of the experimental variance (σ^2) with a term which depends only on the organisation of the tests (A):

$$\text{var}(Y) = A \sigma^2 \quad (1)$$

σ^2 is estimated by repetition of one of the tests.

This estimation is more accurate if the number of repeats is increased. This indicates that the variance of the model can be minimised by choice of an optimal experimental distribution of the tests.

Setting up an experimental design method involves several steps. The nature and limit values of the variables must first be fixed. The degree of the polynomial must then be chosen. Then the matrix is established according to strict rules [8]. In order to facilitate the determination of the relative influence of the different parameters, the variables are expressed in centred, reduced co-ordinates. Their amplitude of variation is therefore confined to the interval [-1,+1].

From a preliminary study on the laminated material the influence of the mass and the velocity on different responses was determined, such as contact time, contact force, central plate displacement, delaminated area between plies of different orientations where appropriate observations were performed to check the number of cracks parallel to plate width (n_1) and the number parallel to the length (n_2) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Orientation of cracks with respect to the laminated plate

This first phase was not intended to establish models of mechanical behaviour but particular attention was directed towards the combination of the two variables mass and velocity. A factorial test matrix is used to study the laminated composite material (Table 1).

Table 1: Two-variable factorial matrix (laminated panels)

Test n°	X ₁	X ₂
1	-1	-1
2	+1	-1
3	-1	+1
4	+1	+1

The model corresponding to this matrix is a first order polynomial for two variables (Eqn 2).

$$Y=b_0+b_1.X_1+b_2.X_2+b_{12}.X_1X_2 \quad (2)$$

The parameter X₁ represents the drop velocity and X₂ is the mass. The coefficient b₁₂ quantifies the coupling between them.

In a second step of the study, a Doehlert matrix [9,10] was used for the sandwich panels. It is a test matrix known as a response surface. The basic principle is to position one point in an experimental domain and to examine the neighbouring area.

These matrices have spherical symmetry. The factors are assumed to be quantitative and known. The Doehlert matrix has the advantage of isovariance in rotation and the ability to be translated in the variables space with a minimum of new tests. It is interesting in case of initial wrong choose of the experimental domain. This last property has not been used in this study.

The three variables in this study for the sandwich panels are respectively the span (X₁), the projectile velocity (X₂) and the mass (X₃). The test matrix associated with these variables requires 13 tests (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Test distribution according to Doehlert matrix with number of tests (sandwich panels)

In addition, the polynomial associated is of second order. This assumes that the responses are non-linear (Eqn 3).

$$Y=b_0+b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3+b_{12}X_1X_2+b_{13}X_1X_3+b_{23}X_2X_3+b_{11}X_1X_1+b_{22}X_2X_2+b_{33}X_3X_3 \quad (3)$$

COMPOSITE PANELS

The laminated composite is composed of glass fibres in an isophthalic polyester resin. The stacking sequence is [0,90]_{4s}. The specimens were manufactured by hand lay up process.

The sandwich skins are made of glass rovimat in polyester, 2mm thick. Two PVC different core foams of the same density, 80 kg/m^3 , were used, each 20 mm thick. These were nominally linear and crosslinked foams. The non reticulated one is considered as ductile (without shear cracks after impact) and the reticulated one as rigid (with shear cracks after impact).

TEST CAMPAIGNS

The impact tests were performed using drop weight set-ups. These involve dropping masses from different heights onto panels which were simply supported on two sides. The end of all strikers is hemispherical with a diameter of 20 mm. In the case of laminated panels, only the drop weight set-up of LA.M.E.F.I.P. (France) has been used. Three systems have been used for the sandwich panels, at LA.M.E.F.I.P. (France), at the Marine Materials Laboratory, IFREMER, Brest (France) and at I.N.E.G.I., Porto, (Portugal) [11].

From the test matrix (Table 1), the test programme is defined (Table 2):

Table 2: Laminate tests

Test n°	Drop height (m)	Mass (kg)
1	0,5	1
2	1,5	1
3	0,5	2
4	1,5	2

For sandwich panels, Table 3 shows the ranges of mass, velocity and span for each test set-up from Doehlert matrix.

Table 3: Experimental domain (sandwich panels)

Laboratory	Impact energy (J)	Mass (kg)	Velocity (m/s)	Span (cm)
LAMEFIP	11 to 100	4 to 7	2 to 6	30 - 80
IFREMER	30 to 300	9 to 24	2 to 6	30 - 80
INEGI	30 to 300	4 to 6	4 to 11	30 - 80

It should be noticed that there are as many polynomials to identify as there are laboratories, for a given response. The sandwich materials were studied in more details as a structure. An additional variable is the span.

The presentation of tools is proposed for dimensioning composite structures, but it should be underlined that these will only be valid within the experimental domains studied, and extrapolation is risky.

For the three laboratories, the same test matrix expressed in centred, reduced co-ordinates is used, independently of the physical domain. Nevertheless, the variables are converted into physical values in accordance with the specific experimental domain of each laboratory.

Three values are linked to the mass variable, five to the span and seven to the velocity. The test parameter which is hardest to modify experimentally is associated with the value changing the least frequently.

An example is given in Table 4 for the Doehlert matrix for sandwich materials at IFREMER.

Table 4: Doehlert matrix for sandwich materials (IFREMER)

Test number	Span (cm)	Velocity (m/s)	Mass (kg)	Impact energy (J)
1	80	4	16.58	133
2	30	4	16.58	133
3	67.5	6	16.58	298
4	42.5	2	16.58	33
5	67.5	2	16.58	33
6	42.5	6	16.58	298
7	67.5	4.6	23.92	253
8	42.5	3.3	9.21	50
9	67.5	3.3	9.21	50
10	55	5.3	9.21	129
11	42.5	4.6	23.92	253
12	55	2.6	23.92	81
13	55	4	16.58	133

RESULTS

Laminated panels

The following results were obtained :

Table 5: Results from impact tests on laminates

Test n°	Load (N)	Deflection (mm)	Contact time (ms)	Delaminated area (cm ²)	n ₁ (cracks)	n ₂ (cracks)
1	1000	8,4	10,0	0	20	37
2	1500	13,3	10,8	0,58	22	70
3	1266	12,9	15,0	1	27	90
4	1900	22,1	15,5	2,28	32	106

From these data the coefficients (Table 6) related to the mass and velocity variables can be determined, together with their coupling (Eqn 2).

Table 6: Representation of coefficients related to each variable

	Load (N)	Deflection of panel (mm)	Contact time (ms)	Delaminated area (cm ²)	n ₁ (cracks)	n ₂ (cracks)
b ₀	1416	14.18	12.8	0.97	25	75
b ₁	283	3.52	0.3	0.47	1.7	12
b ₂	166	3.33	2.4	0.67	4.2	22
b ₁₂	33	1.1	-0.1	0.18	0.7	4.3

In addition, Figure 3 shows that the damage observed is made up essentially of delaminations at several interfaces and cracks oriented parallel to the width and length of the panel (Fig. 1).

Fig. 3: Delamination for laminated panels

Sandwich Panels

Just as for the laminates it is possible, from the test results, to establish the coefficients related to each term of the model for a given response. Among all studied responses, only the contact force between the striker and the panels can be modelled. This last one is the single response which has given some quantitative values for both all the tests of the Doelhart matrix and all laboratories. For example, the measurement of deflection of panels was not always possible, particularly in the case of perforation.

The coefficient values for the contact forces for the two types of foam sandwich are presented (Table 7).

Table 7: Coefficients of the model for contact force for the different laboratories

	IFREMER		I.N.E.G.I.		L.A.M.E.F.I.P.	
	ductile	rigid	ductile	rigid	ductile	rigid
B_0	6666.0	6670.0	6670.0	6516.7	5430.0	5313.3
B_1	319.9	-202.5	-126.2	135.0	-232.5	-262.5
B_2	3373.8	2804.4	2389.5	1271.6	2551.9	2088.6
B_3	2748.5	2077.9	-149.0	130.6	530.7	1051.2
B_{11}	553.1	-155.0	30.0	-941.7	-570.0	356.6
B_{22}	2896.3	3331.8	-990.1	-1118.	-383.3	-913.4
B_{33}	3173.5	630.6	-667.4	-269.9	583.3	281.7
B_{12}	-1409.	-1836.	496.5	98.1	265.6	583.1
B_{13}	4769.2	1126.8	-1467.	-200.0	1155.3	-298.0
B_{23}	1448.9	-697.3	-1941	-108.5	-570.4	756.5

The analysis using this model enables the evolution of the response in the studied experimental domain to be plotted (Fig. 4). Figure 4 shows the model established from the L.A.M.E.F.I.P. test matrix.

Fig. 4: Isovalue plots for contact force measured at LA.M.E.F.I.P. (ductile foam)

The damage processes in these sandwich materials are more complex than those observed in the laminates. Thus it is possible to see upper skin cracking on the impacted side, fibre fracture, then under some test conditions perforation. The core is compressed. Shear cracks at 45° are only noted in the rigid foam (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Cross section in the plane of impact of sandwich with rigid foam (20 mm thick)

More or less debonding of the lower skin is often noted and in some cases perforation. The tests at LA.M.E.F.I.P. helped to study the influence of the core response as local crushing displacement at the impact point was measured [12,13] (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 : Comparison of local crushing of sandwich with rigid or ductile foams (LAMEFIP)

These measurements were completed by observations of damage on the lower skin surfaces (away from the impact) (Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b with a scale equal to 0.5). These two illustrations involve two tests performed at I.N.E.G.I., respectively n°10 (span=55 cm, velocity=9.9 ms⁻¹, mass=3.76 kg) and test n°11 (span=42.5 cm, velocity=8.7 ms⁻¹, mass=5.76 kg) [12]. To quantify this damage mechanism whitened surface areas were measured [11].

Fig.7a: Lower skin damage of sandwich structures for the ductile foam (I.N.E.G.I.)

Fig.7b: Lower skin damage of sandwich structures for the rigid foam (I.N.E.G.I.)

The importance of both mass and velocity in defining the severity of impact is shown in the following example. The comparison between two tests performed at I.N.E.G.I. and IFREMER with the same energy (300 J) but using two different combinations of mass-velocity (Table 9) for two different spans shows a significant difference in the results (Fig.8).

Table 9: Mass-velocity combinations for a 300 J impact for two spans.

	I.N.E.G.I.	IFREMER.
span (cm)	67.5 - 42.5	67.5 - 42.5
mass (kg)	4.76	16.58
velocity (m/s)	11.2	6

Fig. 8: Delaminated area of the lower skin of the rigid foam sandwich panels for a 300 J impact

DISCUSSION

The results concerning the coefficients of the variables mass and velocity of the laminated material indicate (Table 6):

- i) the contact time seems to be independent of the drop velocity as the coefficient of this variable (0.3) is much lower than that of the mass (2.4). Naturally the coefficient of coupling is virtually zero
- ii) for all the other responses the coupling coefficients are significant. This implies that it is not possible to examine the influence of these variables separately. Only a graphical method enables the analysis of the results. However, it appears that the mass and velocity variables are coupled for impact tests in the experimental domain studied here.

For the sandwich materials, the validity of the empirical models must be confirmed. To do this it must be assessed whether the variations of the models are greater than the experimental uncertainties. A variance analysis was therefore performed. This analysis led us to validate only polynomials identified from the L.A.M.E.F.I.P. campaigns.

Even if for the contact force response only the models based on tests at L.A.M.E.F.I.P. are significant, nevertheless, as this response was measured in all three laboratories, it is used to illustrate the results here.

Figure 4 shows the model of this established from the L.A.M.E.F.I.P. test matrix. It enables the joint influence of mass and velocity on the contact force to be evaluated. The isovalue lines are perpendicular to the velocity axis for low velocities. This suggests that the drop velocity dominates the response in this domain. However, when velocity is increased ($>4.5\text{m/s}$) it is the influence of the mass which is more significant.

It is possible to use the models related to each response to analyse their evolution in the experimental domain from a relatively small number of tests (13 tests per laboratory).

The coupling coefficients can rarely be neglected, which confirms the results of the preliminary study on the laminate.

Figure 6 shows that the mechanical behaviour of the core (ductile or rigid) does not significantly affect the local crushing. On the other hand a very significant influence of the type of foam on the damage in the lower skin is apparent (Table 8). There is a much larger delamination in the lower skin of the rigid foam sandwich than in the ductile foam equivalent.

CONCLUSION

The experimental design method enables:

- i) quantitative information to be obtained on the influence of impact parameters, and coupling between variables to be detected
- ii) empirical models for impact responses to be established.

The coupling coefficients for mass and velocity for laminates and sandwich materials are significant for most responses studied. This implies that the energy parameter will not always be sufficient to describe an impact loading.

The nature of the foam core in sandwich materials plays an important role in the development of damage in the lower skin but does not have a strong influence on local crushing under the

striker. Figure 8 clearly shows that the definition of an impact event in terms of an impact energy is ambiguous, both mass and velocity must be specified.

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